

INCREASING THE ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN SOCIETY

¹Kabilova G.R., ²Igamberdieva D.A., ³Shopulotova Z.A., ⁴Kobilova Z.Kh.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10395659>

Abstract. Among many developed countries of the world, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, attention to women and children is manifested in the fact that strengthening their place in society and state management is rising to the level of state policy. In this article, it is important to increase the socio-political activity of women in our country, to ensure that their rights and legal interests are fully respected, to support motherhood and childhood in every way, to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries. information is given about the wide-scale work being carried out to create conditions for its release, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family.

Keywords: family, women, gender equality, activism.

Relevance. The issue of education, which plays an important role in the development of any society, is formed from the family. The family, on the other hand, is the place of relations between husband and wife, parents and children. Therefore, the person who organizes the society is formed on the basis of interdependent relations. In the matter of education and the role of a woman in the family, many examples can be given that already show the long-term proof in practice. In particular, the policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on gender equality opens many opportunities for women in public administration. We can clearly see this even if we look at the constitutional reforms implemented today. Article 58 of the newly adopted constitutional draft law "On the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" guarantees the equal rights of women and men. This is really for men and women in our country, to increase the socio-political activity of women in our country, to ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected, to support motherhood and childhood in every way, to support them in various fields and industries. Extensive work is being done to create conditions for children to realize their abilities and opportunities, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family.

On August 23, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" was adopted. Based on this law, indirect discrimination of women based on gender is prohibited, and positive measures aimed at strengthening the social status of women in society and ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men are strictly defined. The Law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" strengthened the guarantee of equal rights for women and men in the exercise of personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights, in the management of society and state affairs, and equal participation in the election process.

The Committee on Women and Girls and Gender Equality Issues was established in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis. A separate commission on ensuring gender equality was established, and it was decided that it would provide information to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan about the state of affairs in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men. it shows that equal opportunities and conditions are being created.

We can say that the formation of a culture of equality between women and men is a systematic and continuous process that requires cooperation with the general public and civil institutions. In this regard, the joint and coordinated activities of all aspects of society - state

structures, public organizations, business entities, trade unions and the general population - are of great importance. The head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev is adopting a number of decrees, decisions, normative legal documents in order to protect women, provide them with social assistance, and increase the role of women in the fields. In order to find a systematic solution to the problems, to effectively organize and coordinate the activities of competent bodies, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, supporting the neighborhood and religious According to Decree No. PF-81 and Decision No. PQ-146 "On the organization of the activities of the State Committee for Family and Women", the State Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, Tashkent city administrations and district (city) divisions were established. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution" was adopted.

In Uzbekistan, within the framework of "National goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030", one of the priority goals is "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women". - it is necessary to expand programs that support girls in realizing their rights and interests in the socio-economic sphere. In this regard, on March 7, 2022, Decree No. PF-87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women" was adopted.

On the basis of this decree, protection of the rights and legal interests of women in the country, increasing their economic, social and political activity, maintaining their health, providing vocational training and employment, wide involvement in entrepreneurship, social support of needy women in order to support, systematically continue the reforms being carried out to ensure gender equality, as well as to consistently implement the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Global Agenda in 2022-2026 the national program for increasing activity in the fronts was approved. We can cite several reasons for the adoption of this national program. In particular, in recent years, creating equal rights and opportunities for women and men in our country, ensuring their full participation in the management of society and state affairs, socio-economic and legal support, as well as oppression and Although large-scale reforms aimed at protection from violence have been carried out, during the transition of Uzbekistan to a new stage of development, it is necessary to raise the system of comprehensive support for all women to a higher level and to promote women's participation in society. It is becoming more important to increase its role. However, today the following problems remain in supporting women and further increasing their social activity:

studying the problems of women, especially women in rural areas, training unemployed women in professions that are in high demand in the labor market, providing them with work, involving them in family and private entrepreneurship, handicrafts work is not systematically implemented;

providing socio-legal, psychological and material assistance to women in need of help and who have fallen into a serious social situation, including women with disabilities and elderly women in need of care, aimed at removing them from the state of need things are not organized efficiently;

the scope of activities aimed at increasing the legal culture of women, eliminating the factors and conditions that caused violations committed by them, and promoting the legal consequences is insufficient;

Advocacy and methodological and practical training on the procedures for providing preferential loans (including micro-loans) to women in need of social protection and low-income families for effective use of homestead land, allocation of subsidies to them, and provision of employment. There are weaknesses in the coordination system.

The main goal of the newly adopted national program is to further strengthen the system of social protection of women, to strengthen their health, to create the necessary conditions for girls' education, to educate talented and educated girls and to increase their scientific potential. improvement of the legal basis for protection of women's rights and legal interests, increase of socio-economic and political activity of women, strengthening of their role in society, especially in state administration, and ensuring gender equality.

In addition, it is planned to carry out the following activities within the framework of the national program:

- Ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men;
- Further strengthening the guarantees of women's labor rights;
- Protection of women from oppression and violence;
- Strengthening the role and status of women in state and community management;
- Creating additional conditions for women's education, increasing the role of women in the field of science;

Carrying out fundamental, practical and innovative research on issues of strengthening and development of the family institution;

Ensuring legality and law and order among women, prevention of offenses and implementation of modern methods and forms of combating crime.

Conclusion. After the implementation of the national program, the following results are expected:

The number of women participating in the "One Million Programmers" project will be increased to 30%;

cooperatives will be established in 14 regions in order to support the socio-economic development of the regions and the employment of women;

The percentage of women among the candidates recommended for the master's degree at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is up to 30%;

the parameters of admission to higher educational institutions in areas where there is a high need for psychologists will be increased by 30%;

inter-district perinatal centers will be established on the basis of 46 maternity departments of district (city) medical associations;

the scope of covering more than 337,000 women living in the republic with medical, social and professional rehabilitation measures will be expanded, mechanisms for outpatient rehabilitation will be introduced in their rehabilitation and prosthetics centers;

the legal basis for the protection of women's rights and legal interests will be improved, the implementation of international conventions and national legal norms will be strictly controlled;

women with disabilities or children with disabilities, homeless women, women without breadwinners, and women who need the care of others are supported in every way.

In conclusion, increasing the socio-political activity of women is one of the important factors of the reforms implemented in our country.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-81 of March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, and supporting the neighborhood and clergy"
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 "On measures to further accelerate work on the systematic support of families and women"